

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE**Himmatova Nodira Normamatovna**

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Determining the content of teaching a foreign language is impossible without referring to psychology - the science of the patterns of mental reflection of reality in the human mind, which studies the mental properties, mental activity and state of the individual, depending on the conditions in which they manifest themselves. Psychology deals with the structure of human speech activity and its formation. A science dealing with the study of the structure of speech activity arose - psycholinguistics. Psycholinguists study the speech behavior of a person, describe models of mental processes, operations, actions that occur when listening and speaking. Psycholinguists make attempts to establish which language units and in what sequence take part in encoding (speaking) and decoding (listening) sentences. When teaching a foreign language, educational (cognitive) activities are formed, during which the student learns the language, speech mechanisms are formed in him, and communication activities, during which he uses the language.

Like any activity, speech activity (RD) must have its own subject. Such a subject of RD is a thought (meaningful plan of utterance). The activity finds implementation in specific actions and operations that ensure the operation of the corresponding speech mechanisms responsible for listening, speaking, reading and writing. Speech action acts as an object of learning in the activity approach and in communicative orientation.

In psychology, speech action is defined as the process of interaction of its components (participants in communication; communicative intention or goal; subject content: topics, situations; linguistic means; extralinguistic and paralinguistic means) aimed at generating an utterance in a specific communication situation. Dialogues, conversations, texts, any oral and written speech products materialize only as a result of speech actions. [7]

Speech actions, however, are possible when the possession of language and speech material at each point of the educational process is brought to the level of skills and abilities. As you know, the interpretation of skills and abilities is given in psychology. S.L. Rubinstein defines skills as automated components of a consciously performed activity, formed through exercises and training. The physiological basis of skills according to I.P. Pavlov is a dynamic stereotype. A.A. Leontiev considers speech operations to be speech skills, the implementation of

which has been brought to a degree of perfection. Knowledge of a foreign language is the possession of a system of speech skills. Language exists in the human psyche primarily in the form of skills that can be implemented at any time. For the implementation of communication of insufficiently formed speech skills, speech skills are necessary. Skills involve creativity. It is connected with thinking, imagination, emotions. E.I. Passov made an attempt to "breed" skills and abilities. By skill, he understands "relatively independent actions in the system of conscious activity, which, thanks to the totality of qualities, have become one of the conditions for the performance of this activity." The ability is defined by him as follows: it is "a conscious activity based on a system of subconsciously functioning actions and aimed at solving communicative problems." [10]

So, psychology allows you to determine the psychological component of the content of teaching a foreign language at school - this is the formation of skills and abilities to use the language being studied for communicative purposes.

5 psychological problems of learning English

How often English teachers have to hear from their frustrated students: "I can't do anything!", "I will never learn to speak English!". Many of them sincerely believe that everyone, absolutely everyone around them speaks and writes better and more correctly than they do, and the situation is irreparable. If you have ever had such thoughts, read our article.

The five psychological problems most commonly experienced by English learners are:

#1 self-doubt

"Everyone speaks English better than me," is the thought that comes to the mind of almost every English learner.

It is obvious that this is not the case. And is it possible to correctly evaluate your own linguistic knowledge?

The fact is that many people speak not so much correctly as confidently - more confidently than you. And this does not mean that they know English better. Self-confidence can and should be developed: if you work on yourself in this direction, you will see how your whole life will change for the better.

One of the features of the English character is equanimity, the ability not to endure feelings for show. And for this you need extraordinary acting skills! Try to try on this image for yourself: in the end, no one will guess about the storm in your soul, if outwardly you radiate calmness and tranquility.

#2 Failing to set realistic goals

It is also worth remembering that "no one will embrace the immensity." At the beginning of learning English, you will have to determine the primary goal of your efforts and focus only on it - be it the ability to conduct a dialogue in English (classes with a Skype tutor will help you with this), understand unadapted speech, or learn to read and translate English texts with a dictionary. Start from the main task that you face: if you are learning English for work, focus on professional vocabulary. At the same time, for some time you may not pay special attention to pronunciation or vocabulary expansion outside of the chosen specialization - limit yourself to mastering the basic words and expressions in the area you need.

If you "disperse", try to achieve high results in several areas at once, your successes may not be so noticeable, first of all, to yourself - and this affects the motivation and desire to continue what you started.

#3 Fear of making a mistake

"I'm embarrassed to speak to native speakers because I'm afraid to make a mistake," are words English teachers hear very often. Too often!

You don't have to take your mistakes to heart, because, by and large, your main task is to correctly convey your thought. By the way, the average Englishman or American in terms of native language proficiency is also, as they say, "not a standard" - mistakes are common even to native speakers.

In addition, we all know that English-speaking countries are a "motley cauldron" of different nationalities and cultures, so a person with imperfect knowledge of the language or a noticeable accent is treated absolutely loyally. Moreover, a foreign accent is often perceived as a charming detail that attracts interested attention to its owner.

Of course, we all understand that the more fully and accurately you can express your thought, the better. But the fear of making a mistake negatively affects the development of your speaking skills - you can hardly argue with that.

So don't be afraid to make mistakes (you've probably heard this hundreds of times, but that doesn't stop the truth from being true). And don't be embarrassed if someone corrects you - that's how you get closer to the ideal.

#4 Fear of public speaking

"I'm afraid to speak in class because I'm embarrassed by my classmates." Obviously, group classes are not suitable for you. Look for an alternative - it is better to study English with a tutor or on your own.

Fear of public speaking (or otherwise stage fright, stage fear, stage fright) spoils the lives of many people around the world, even if they speak their native

language. This is a well-known phobia and your task, if not to overcome, then outwit it. And in this case, think about teaching one-on-one: with an experienced and tactful teacher, you will achieve results faster, especially if it is a native speaker.

You can also take group English courses when you feel more confident. The relatively low price and availability of courses speaks in their favor; in addition, communication in a group contributes to the development of colloquial speech. But don't forget that your fellow practitioners can also make mistakes, so don't limit yourself to just this type of communication.

#5 Fear of being funny

"I'm afraid to make a mistake because I will be laughed at."

Have you ever laughed at a person who tries to speak Russian and does not do it perfectly? This can be difficult to admit, but - most likely, yes. There are mistakes that cannot be heard with a straight face. Here are some examples:

I am like a sandwich. (instead of "I like sandwiches.")

I visited my ankle. (instead of "I visited my uncle.")

In the morning, I get up at seven o'clock, clean my tooth, have breakfast and go to work. (instead of teeth)

A nurse looks for people in hospital. (instead of "A nurse looks after people in hospital": to look for - look for, to look after - take care, care)

Feel free to contact me if you cause any problems. (to cause - to be the cause, cause)

Therefore, be more tolerant of those who no, no, yes, and laugh at you: after all, any of those who study a language have made such a mistake at least once in their life. It's a shame? Yes. But abandoning your plans in fear of making a mistake is even more offensive. So - away the fear! Fears come and go, but knowledge remains. Who does not risk - he does not know English!

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